

Dear Sir / ma'am,

I am Nagaraj from India. Currently I am working in DiFACTO Robotics & Automation Pvt. Ltd, Bangalore, India. The concept I would like to speak is about collision of robots & it is named as Zero Collision Robot.

ABSTRACT

In the present world there are many robots which are based on different principles but still there occurs a collision at many points (It may be collision of arms of the same robot or b/w two robots).

In modern Collaborative Robots, the robot will detect the collision in advance & stops the further motion of the robot arm until a human corrects it. But the concept of Zero Collision Robots is to detect the collision in advance and to take the preventive measures for avoiding the accident without any human interference i.e., by itself.

Thank You and Best regards,

Nagaraj.S

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